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INSURANCE RELATIONS: NATURE AND BOUNDARIES

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Annotation. *This article notes that insurance is a special complex economic category and a system of economic relations in the transfer (transformation) of risks aimed at the formation of targeted funds to compensate for damage (loss). Based on the research and analysis of a number of scientific literature, through the prism of economics, the author argues that the nature of insurance relations consists in the redistribution of risks transferred to the insurer on the basis of a contract, which ensures financial stability, and the boundaries of insurance, including the need for the occurrence of an insured event, are determined by the presence of insurance interest and the possibility of risk assessment, which differ from other financial and credit mechanisms. In this context, the relevance of this study is determined by a set of theoretical, methodological and practical problems related to the development of theoretical and empirical knowledge on the problems of insurance relations, the need for their regulation, and the development of proposals to improve their competitiveness in general.*

Keywords: *insurance, insurance premium, insurance services, insurance risk, specific features of insurance, insurance fund, insurance fund funds, volume of insurance services, insurance relationship, nature of insurance relations, boundaries of insurance relations, objects of insurance relations, insurance industry, economic interest.*

СТРАХОВЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ: ПРИРОДА И ГРАНИЦЫ

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Аннотация. *В данной статье отмечается, что страхование представляет собой особую комплексную экономическую категорию и систему экономических отношений при трансфере (трансформации) рисков, направленных на формирование целевых денежных фондов для возмещения ущерба (убытка). Автор на основе исследования и анализа ряда научных литератур, через призму экономики, утверждает, что природа страховых отношений заключаются в перераспределении рисков, переданных страховщику на основе договора, что обеспечивает финансовую устойчивость, а границы страхования, включающие в себя необходимость случайности наступления страхового события, определяются наличием страхового интереса и возможностью оценки риска, отличающие от иных финансово-кредитных механизмов.*

В этом контексте актуальность данного исследования обуславливаются комплексом теоретико-методологических и практических проблем, связанных с развитием теоретико-эмпирических знаний по проблемам страховых отношений, потребности в их регулировании, выработке предложений по повышению их конкурентоспособности в целом.

Ключевые слова: *страхование, страховая премия, страховые услуги, страховой риск, специфические особенности страхования, страховой фонд, средства страхового*

фонда, объема страховых услуг, страховое отношение, природа страховых отношений, границы страховых отношений, объекты страховых отношений, отрасли страхования, экономический интерес.

СУГУРТА МУНОСАБАТЛАРИНИНГ ТАБИАТИ ВА ЧЕГАРАЛАРИ

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада суғурта - бу ўзига хос мураккаб иқтисодий категория ва иқтисодий муносабатлар тизими сифатида кўрилиши эҳтимол бўлган зарар(йўқотиш)ни қоплашга йўналтириладиган мақсадли маблағлар фондиди шакллантиришига қаратилган риск трансфери ва трансформацияси жараёнлари тарзидида талқин этилган.

Муаллиф, қатор илмий ишланмалар таҳлили асносида суғурта муносабатларининг табиати ва чегараси хусусида, шу жумладан, молиявий барқарорликни таъминлашга қаратилган шартнома асосида суғуртачи зиммасига ўтказилган риск(лар)ни тақсимлаш ва қайта тақсимлаш жараёнларидан иборат эканлигини таъкидлайди, суғуртанинг зарурати ва ундан манфаатдорлик рискни баҳолаш имконияти билан белгиланишига кўра, молия ва кредит муносабатларидан фарқланишига алоҳида тўхталиб ўтган.

Ушбу тадқиқотнинг долзарблиги суғурта муносабатлари муаммоларига дахлдор назарий-эмпирик билимларни ривожлантириши, назарий-услубий ва амалий ечимлар ишлаб чиқилиши замирида суғурта хизматларининг рақобатбардошлигини ошириши билан изоҳланади.

Калит сўзлар. суғурта, суғурта мукофоти, суғурта rischi, суғуртанинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари, суғурта хизматлари, суғурта хизматлари ҳажми, суғурта фонди, суғурта фонди маблағлари, суғурта муносабатлари, суғурта муносабатлари табиати, суғурта муносабатлари чегаралари, суғурта муносабатлари объектлари, суғурта соҳаси, иқтисодий манфаатдорлик.

Introduction.

In the third decade of the 21st century, in the context of globalization, fundamental fundamental changes are observed in the economy of Uzbekistan associated with digital transformation, the penetration of innovations, climate change, which inevitably leads to a change in the meaning and understanding of insurance relations, accompanied by the optimization of the management system as a whole.

Today, insurance is a special complex economic category and a system of economic relations in the transfer (transformation) of risks, aimed at the formation of special-purpose monetary funds to compensate for damage (loss).

In scientific and theoretical developments, a significant number of definitions have been formulated that the nature of insurance relations is a specific relationship that consists in the transfer and transformation of risks transferred to the insurer (reinsurer) on the basis of a contract, which ensures the financial stability of the entities as a whole.

And in this context, the boundaries of insurance are determined by economic feasibility, the presence of insurance interest and the possibility of risk assessment, which differ from other financial and credit mechanisms, and include the need for the accident of the occurrence of an insured event, which allows us to consider as specific relations, which as an independent economic category.

The development of insurance relations in the context of globalization of the economy

causes the need for its analytical comprehension. A set of theoretical, methodological and practical problems associated with the development of theoretical and empirical scientific knowledge on the problematic issue of insurance relations, the need for their regulation, including the development of proposals to increase the competitiveness of services in competition, determine the relevance of this study.

Analysis of literature.

In economic studies, various points of view on insurance relations as a complex economic category are presented and a significant number of their definitions are formulated.

The development of theories of insurance relations and individual components of theories is presented in the works of foreign scientists Abramov V.Y.²⁹, Arkhipova E.R.³⁰, Borch K.³¹, Briys E.³², Buhmann H.³³, Chiu W. H.³⁴, Courbage Ch.,³⁵ Dionne G.³⁶, Ehrlich J.³⁷, Eling M.³⁸, Greent M.R.³⁹, Gomelli V.B.⁴⁰, Kaas R.⁴¹, Konshina F.V.⁴², Orlanyuk-Malitskoy L.A.⁴³, Shauhin A.⁴⁴, Shakhova V.V.⁴⁵, Yuldasheva R.T.⁴⁶ etc.

In the works of a number of researchers, insurance relations were considered only as an auxiliary tool for regulating the economy. According to F.V. Konshin, insurance relations "... is

²⁹Abramov, V.Y. Insurance: Theory and Practice: Monograph /190 V.Yu. – Moscow: Wolters Kluwer, 2007-504 p.

³⁰Arkhipov, A.P. Insurance. Modern Course: Textbook / A.P. Arkhipov, V.G. Gomellya, D.S. Tulenty; edited by E.V. Kolomin. - 2nd edition – Moscow: Finance and Statistics. 2014. - 448 p.

³¹Borch, K. Economics of Insurance / K. Borch. – Amsterdam: North-Holland, 1990. – P. 402.

³²Briys, E. Risk aversion and the propensities for self- insurance and self-protection / E. Briys, H. Schlesinger // Southern Economic Journal. – 1990. - № 2. - P. 458-467.

³³Buhrmann, H. Mathematical methods of risk theory / H. Buhrmann. – Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg, 1970. – P. 210.

³⁴Chiu, W.H. On the propensity to self-protect / W.H. Chiu // Journal of Risk and Insurance. – 2000. - № 4. - P. 555-577.

³⁵Courbage, Ch. Self-insurance. Self-protection and market insurance within the dual theory of choice / Ch. Courbage // The GENEVA Papers on Risk and Insurance Theory. - 2001. – № 1. Volume 26. – P. 43-56.

³⁶Dionne, G. Handbook of Insurance / G. Dionne. – Boston: Kluwer Academic Publishers. - 2000. - P. 927// <https://books.google.ru/books?id=apd-gSAlhuIC&printsec=frontcover&hl=ru#v=onepage&q&f=false>.

³⁷Ehrlich, J. Market Insurance, Self-Insurance and Self-Protection / J. Ehrlich, G. Becker // Journal of Political Economy. – 1972. - № 4. Volume 80. - P. 623-648.

³⁸Eling, M. The impact of digitalization on the insurance value chain and the insurability of risks / M. Eling, M. Lehmann // The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance-Issues and Practice. - 2018. - № 43 (3). - P. 359-396. // https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321636110_The_Impact_of_Digitalization_on_the_Insurance_Value_Chain_in_and_the_Insurability_of_Risks.

³⁹Greent, M.R. Risk and Insurance / M.R. Greent, J.S. Trieschmann. - Cincinnati: South-Western Pub. Co., 1984. - P. 648.

⁴⁰Gomellya V.B. Genesis of Insurance in the Commodity Economy: Monograph / V.B. Gomellya. – Moscow: Ankil, 2018. – 252 p.

⁴¹Kaas, R. Modern Actuarial Risk Theory / R. Kaas, M. Goovaerts, J. Dhaene, M. Denuit. – London: Springer Heidelberg Dordrecht [2nd ed]. - 2009. – P. 393. https://faculty.ksu.edu.sa/sites/default/files/modern_actuarial_risk_theory.pdf.

⁴²Konshin F.V. Gosudarstvennoye strakhovanie v SSSR: uchebnik dlya finansovo-ekonomicheskikh vysshikh uchebnykh zavedeniy [State insurance in the USSR: a textbook for financial and economic higher educational institutions]. – Moscow: Gosfinizdat, 1949. – 404 p

⁴³Orlanyuk-Malitskaya L.A. Nauchnaya shkola "Strakhovanie" Finovuniversiteta: istoriya i sovremennost' [Scientific school "Insurance" of the Financial University: history and modernity] / L.A. Orlanyuk-Malitskaya // Strakhovoe delo. – 2019. – № 3 (312). – P. 50–59.

⁴⁴Shauhin, A. New Institutional Theory of Insurance / A. Shauhin, A. Talesh // UC Irvine Law Review. – 2015. - № 3. Volume 5. - P. 617-650.

⁴⁵Shakhov V.V. Insurance as an Independent Economic Category / V.V. Shakhov // Bulletin of the Financial Academy. – 1998. – № 1 (5). – P. 20–29.

⁴⁶Yuldashev R.T. Sistemnyy analiz ponyatii «strakhovanie» i «strakhovoy fond»: razmyshleniya uchenogo ekonomika po aktual'nym probleme ekonomicheskogo teorii, istorii i sovremennosti [System analysis of the concepts of "insurance" and "insurance fund": reflections of a scientist economist on actual problems of economic theory, history and modernity. – 2013. – № 4. – S. 201–213.

one of the methods of creating a centralized insurance fund for compensation at the expense of insurance premiums for losses in the national economy from natural disasters and accidents, as well as for the payment of appropriate amounts in connection with the occurrence of events related to the life and working capacity of the insured."⁴⁷

A different attitude to the nature of insurance relations is demonstrated by later researchers. In this context, M.K. Shermenev offers another definition, according to which insurance relations "... are economic relations arising in connection with the formation (at the expense of the owner of the property) and the use of the insurance fund created by a special organization (insurer) to compensate the participants of the insurance fund (insured) for damage from natural disasters and other unforeseen events."⁴⁸

In other sources, insurance relations are defined as "... a system of measures for the creation of a monetary insurance fund at the expense of the contributions of its participants, from the resources of which damage caused by a natural disaster, accidents is compensated, as well as other amounts are paid in connection with the occurrence of certain events."⁴⁹

There is a group of definitions that represent insurance relations as an aggregate relationship in economic activity based on compensation and solidarity, which has as its goal "... covering a future need or need caused by the occurrence of an accidental and at the same time statistically perceptible event."⁵⁰ This definition is based on the signs of reciprocity and retribution through association, i.e., an organized group of persons. The economic category of insurance is a part of finance, its specific features serve as an objective prerequisite for the inclusion of insurance relations as an independent sphere in the financial system."⁵¹

Others are of the opinion that "... Insurance is not only a financial, but partly also a credit category." ⁵²There is an opinion that "... insurance belongs to the sphere of exchange, since it provides services." ⁵³Academician K.G. Vobly refers insurance to distribution, believing that "... insurance as an economic measure to protect the integrity of the property fund should be considered in connection with distribution."⁵⁴ L.I. Reitman notes that "... insurance is an economic category that is subordinate to the category of finance."⁵⁵

In the economic studies of Uzbek scientists, such as Kh.Shennaeva⁵⁶, I. Abdurakhmonova⁵⁷, Koldosheva⁵⁸, T. Baimuratova⁵⁹ and others, taking into account the stable growth of insurance activities, various points of view on insurance relations as a complex economic category are presented, and a significant number of their definitions are formulated on the basis of the current trend in the context of transformation to the world market. For example, in some studies It is noted that "... Insurance is associated with the application of relations as such,

⁴⁷[Konshin F.V. Gosudarstvennoe strakhovanie v SSSR \[State insurance in the USSR\]. - 4th ed., revised and supplemented Moscow, Gosfinizdat, 1961. P.12 \(- 336 p.\).](#)

⁴⁸[Shermenev M.K. Financial Reserves as a Factor of Planned Development of the Socialist Economy. Abstract of diss. for the degree of Doctor of Economics, Moscow, 1971. P. 21.](#)

⁴⁹Soviet Economic Dictionary. Soviet Encyclopedia Publishing House, Moscow, 1990, p. 291 (-1642 p.).

⁵⁰Romanova T.F. Insurance: Theory, Practice. - Rostov-on-Don: RGEA, 1998. P. 12 (- 199 p.)

⁵¹Ibid., p. 13.

⁵²Reitman L.I. Strakhovoe delo: uchebnik [Insurance business: textbook]. - Moscow: Banking and Exchange Scientific Advisory Center, 1992. P. 15 (- 530 p.).

⁵³Pylov K.N. Categories of Insurance // Vestnik ROSS. 1993. No 1, p. 34.

⁵⁴Vobly K.G. Fundamentals of Insurance Economics. Moscow: Publishing Center "Ankil", 1995. P. 27 (- 228 p.).

⁵⁵Reitman L.I. Strakhovoe delo [Insurance Business]. Moscow, ROST Publ., 2007. P. 13 (- 377 p.).

⁵⁶Shenayev X.M. O‘zbekiston Respublikasida sug‘urta faoliyatini rivojlantirish yo‘nalishlari. Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. avtoreferati. – T.: TMI, 2021. -135 b.

⁵⁷Abduraxmonov I.X. O‘zbekiston Respublikasida javobgarlikni sug‘urtalashning amaliyotini takomillashtirish. i.f.n. ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. avtoreferati. – T.: BMA, 2010,

⁵⁸Quldashev K.M. O‘zbekistonda o‘zaro sug‘urtalashning metodologik asoslarini takomillashtirish. Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. avtoreferati. – T.: TMI, 2020.

⁵⁹Baymurotov T.M. O‘zbekistonda sug‘urta faoliyati va uni soliqqa tortish mexanizmini takomillashtirish, i.f.n. ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. avtoreferati. – T.: Davlat va jamiyat qurilishi akademiyasi, 2004, -24 b.

which is organized in order to compensate for damage caused by unforeseen events, ... represent the sum of economic relations."⁶⁰

And in other studies, in particular, it is noted that "as a system of relations to protect the property interests of the population, economic entities, as well as the state, insurance implies the need to make insurance payments from the funds formed at the expense of insurance premiums of trust funds at the occurrence of insured events in the life and activities of economic entities, determined by law. The interconnection of the interests of the parties participating in insurance is expressed in the implementation of a system of institutional-distributive relations regarding compensation for damage in accordance with the amount of liability that is due to the very economic nature of insurance..."⁶¹

In our opinion, the above definitions do not show the economic content of the category of insurance as an integral part of production relations. The seeming similarity with lending relations to insurance is given by such a feature as the repayment of insurance payments. However, it applies only to life insurance, in which most of the premiums (net payments) are returned upon the occurrence of an insured event (survival of the insured to a certain date or in the event of his death). But with property insurance, accident insurance and other types of insurance, insurance compensation is paid only upon the occurrence of an insured event and in the amount stipulated by the contract.

The economic content of these payments is different from the return of insurance payments. In our opinion, the most justified and consistent with the economic essence of insurance in the modern economy is the approach of V.V. Shakhov, who argues that insurance should be considered as an independent economic category (in his opinion, "... Insurance is a system of economic relations, including a set of forms and methods for the formation of trust funds and their use to compensate for damage in the event of various unforeseen adverse phenomena, as well as to provide assistance to citizens in the event of certain events in their lives." ⁶²We base this conclusion on the fact that "... Insurance has its own economic content and corresponding forms of manifestation, which, in our opinion, is more typical for a separate economic category."⁶³

In scientific publications, despite the presence of practical examples, there is an insufficient theoretical understanding of the possibility of implementing insurance relations outside the traditionally formed and normatively fixed circle of their participants in the insurance market, there is no explanation of insurance relations outside the insurance market in the theory of insurance, and the possible impact of this phenomenon on the development of the insurance market is not analyzed.

Results.

Today, the insurance industry plays an extremely important role in the economy. The development of insurance relations in the economy causes the need for its analytical comprehension. Acting in the form of money, consolidating these relations by economic and legal norms, insurance has features that connect it with the categories of "finance", "credit", and at the same time performs functions characteristic only for it and its inherent role, which allows us to consider as specific relations, which as an independent economic category.

The transformation of the economy into a market economy has changed the nature of the activities of producers, increasing both the level of risk and uncertainty and the degree of their responsibility for the results of target activities. Producers, economic entities of various forms of

⁶⁰Shenayev X.M. O‘zbekiston Respublikasida sug‘urta faoliyatini rivojlantirish yo‘nalishlari. Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. avtoreferati. – T.: TMI, 2021. -135 b.

⁶¹Riskology: Textbook. Part IV / T.M. Baymurov; – T.: "Iqtisod-Moliya", 2021. P.171-172 (– 300 p.).

⁶²Shakhov V.V. Insurance: A Textbook for Higher Educational Institutions. Moscow, UNITY Publ., 2003. P. 16 (– 311 p.).

⁶³Gubar O. V., Kukhmirov P. S. Impact of property transformation on the dynamics of insurance relations in Russia: Monograph. Rostov-on-Don: RSUE "RINH", 2000. - 167 p.

ownership, acting as insurers, feel the need not only to compensate for traditional economic damage due to damage (loss) of fixed and current assets, but also to compensate for lost profits or additional costs due to forced downtime of an economic entity (irregular supply of raw materials, insolvency of subcontractors). But it is known that the required condition for the normal reproduction process is its continuity and uninterruptedness. Under the influence of changes in economic interests, the nature of insurance also changes.

Insurance is increasingly “... as one of the means of ensuring economic freedom and individual rights in a market economy.”⁶⁴ There is a gradual formation of the insurance market - one of the mandatory elements of the market infrastructure.

In this context, it should be noted that in Uzbekistan, the insurance market is actively developing, showing an increase in the volume of insurance services, while the main types of insurance include auto insurance, cargo and property insurance, as well as accident insurance. To date, the capacity of the Uzbek insurance market, i.e., the insurance penetration rate is only 0.8% of GDP (Fig. 1), while Taiwan is the leader in this parameter. where insurance premiums provide 19% of GDP, Hong Kong (17%), South Africa (14%), South Korea (13%) and Finland (12%). In the United States and Japan, the value of this indicator is 9.5-10%, in the EU countries, the ratio of insurance premiums to GDP is on average 8%, in Latin America, Eastern Europe and Africa - 2-3.5%.⁶⁵

Fig. 1. Share of total insurance premiums to GDP in Uzbekistan (%)⁶⁶

In Uzbekistan, the value of this indicator was in the range from 0.32 to 0.9%. Despite the increase in insurance premiums for the above years, their volume is currently less than one percent compared to the country's GDP. In the world, this figure averages 7.3 percent⁶⁷.

It should be noted that over the above years, the insurance market has shown an increase in premiums, but the level of insurance penetration is still estimated as low compared to developed countries.

According to the forecasts of analysts of the international reinsurance company Swiss Re, taking into account the global cataclysms and geopolitical conflicts that put pressure on economic growth, in particular, in Europe, the dynamic development of the insurance industry in Asia is expected (Table 1).

For example, in the coming decade, "India will become one of the fastest growing markets in the world. Statistical analysis of specialists clearly shows that the United States has become the world leader in terms of the total volume of insurance premiums - 2.7 trillion dollars (Table 1).

⁶⁴Gvozdenko A.A. Fundamentals of Insurance. Moscow: Finance and Statistics, 1998, p. 211 (- 304 p.).

⁶⁵Sigma: World insurance: the recovery gains pace. <https://www.swissre.com/dam/jcr:ca792993-80ce-49d7-9e4f-7e298e399815/swiss-reinstitute-sigma-3-2021-en.pdf>

⁶⁶Compiled by the author on the basis of dataUzDaily; <https://napp.uz/ru/news/sostavlen-reyting-strahovshchikov-po-kachestvu-okazyvaemyh-strahovyh-uslug>, as well as <https://govinfo.uz/state/state-statistics-agency>.

⁶⁷<https://tradingeconomics.com/united-states/life-insurance-premium-volume-to-gdp-percnt-wb-data>

Table. 1

TOP ten countries in the world by total insurance premiums (2022)⁶⁸

№	Country	Volume of premiums, in US dollars	Increased/decreased, %.
1.	USA	2 718 699 000 000	8,1
2.	China	696 128 000 000	6,1
3.	Japan	403 592 000 000	-2,6
4.	United Kingdom	399 142 000 000	16,7
5.	France	296 380 000 000	24
6.	Germany	275 779 000 000	5,9
7.	South Korea	193 008 000 000	1,5
8.	Italy	192 481 000 000	11,5
9.	Canada	161 289 000 000	15,8
10.	India	126 974 000 000	13,5

In second and third place were China and Japan - \$696.1 billion and \$403.5 billion, respectively. These three markets accounted for almost 56% of global premiums⁶⁹ as a whole.

In second and third place were China and Japan - \$696.1 billion and \$403.5 billion, respectively. These three markets accounted for almost 56% of global premiums⁷⁰ as a whole.

Currently, according to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Insurance Activities" (Chapter 2, Article 6), insurance is divided into the following industries (Fig. 2):

- life insurance;
- General insurance.

Fig. 2. Industries and types (classes) of insurance⁷¹

Insurers are not only property owners, but also other legal entities and individuals responsible for its safety. The terms and conditions of insurance of other people's property and one's own property may differ significantly, which is reflected in specific insurance rules. Property

⁶⁸Swiss Re Institute// www.swissre.com/institute

⁶⁹<https://www.swissre.com/institute/research/sigma-research/>

⁷⁰Ibid.

⁷¹Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 23.11.2021 "On Insurance Activities". No ZRU-730 (National Database of Legislation, 24.11.2021, No 03/21/730/1089)// <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5739120>.

insurance reflects the probabilistic nature of damage to property as a result of natural disasters and other unforeseen events.

In accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the objects of insurance relations can be (Fig. 3):

Fig. 3. Objects of insurance relations⁷²

- the objects of life insurance may be property interests related to the survival of individuals to a certain age or term or the occurrence of other events in the life of individuals, as well as their death, or property interests related to harm to the health of individuals, as well as their death as a result of an accident or illness;

⁷²Compiled by the author, in accordance with the Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 23.11.2021 "On Insurance Activities". No ZRU-730 (National Database of Legislation, 24.11.2021, No 03/21/730/1089))// <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5739120>).

- the objects of medical insurance may be property interests related to payment for the organization and provision of medical (medical care, provision of medicines) and other services as a result of a person's health disorder or condition of a person requiring the organization and provision of such services, as well as the implementation of preventive measures that reduce the degree of threats dangerous to the life or health of a person and (or) eliminate them;

- the objects of property insurance may be property interests associated with the risk of loss (destruction), shortage or damage to property;

- the objects of financial risk insurance in property insurance may be the property interests of the insured (insured person) associated with the risk of non-receipt of income, the occurrence of unforeseen expenses of individuals and legal entities;

- the objects of business risk insurance may be property interests associated with the risk of losses from entrepreneurial activity due to the failure of the entrepreneur's counterparties to fulfill their obligations or changes in the conditions of this activity due to circumstances beyond the control of the entrepreneur, including the risk of not receiving the expected income;

- the objects of civil liability insurance can be property interests related to:
the risk of liability for causing harm to the life, health or property of individuals, the property of legal entities, the state;

the risk of liability for violation of the terms of the contract.

The importance of insurance is determined by the size of the insurance premium per capita. In recent years, each inhabitant of our planet has about 650-700 US dollars of insurance premium. At the same time, the average per capita insurance costs in emerging markets are about \$150, of which 54% are life insurance premiums and 46% are non-life insurance premiums.

In the EU countries, residents spend an average of 3 thousand US dollars per year on insurance. In Latin America and Eastern Europe, it is \$200-600. In countries such as Canada and the United States - over 4 thousand dollars a year.

In Uzbekistan, at the end of 2024, the volume of insurance premiums per capita amounted to only 288.7 thousand sums (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Dynamics of the share of insurance premiums per capita in Uzbekistan, thousand sums⁷³

In 2024, the insurance sector grew by 21.2%, reaching a volume of 9.77 trillion sums. Almost 98% of all premiums are for general insurance, while life insurance accounts for only 2.45% of the market portfolio. In this case, it should be noted that the density of insurance is growing in general, but despite this, it still accounts for an insignificant part of the total income per capita, which in 2025 amounted to about 29.9 million sums per year.

The current situation with the share of total insurance premiums in GDP and insurance premiums per capita in Uzbekistan is mainly explained by insufficient insurance literacy and

⁷³Compiled by the author based on UzDaily data; <https://napp.uz/ru/news/sostavlen-reyting-strahovshchikov-po-kachestvu-okazyvaemyh-strahovyh-uslug>, as well as <https://govinfo.uz/state/state-statistics-agency>.

distrust of legal entities and individuals in insurance as an element of the risk management system.

In terms of their economic essence, the insurance industries are united in that in both types there are closed vapor distribution relations between the subjects of the insurance fund - a reserve of money and (or) material resources to cover damage. They differ in that in life insurance, the relationship between the insurer and the insured is not related to any property. In liability insurance, the relationship between the insurer and the insured is formed on the basis of the use of certain property, but their content does not depend on the value of this property.

There is a lot of empirical evidence that the development of finance has a significant impact on economic growth, even taking into account other key factors. The mechanism of this influence lies in one of the most important functions performed by financial systems in general and the institution of insurance in particular - the function of reducing and distributing risk among a set of economic agents. In this context, risk diversification is the most important need of subjects and individuals in the modern economic system with its numerous ramified connections and complex contractual relations.

Considering the historically formed institution of finance, it is still necessary to clarify what the essence of insurance is as a special element of this system. For this purpose, it is necessary to identify the specific features of insurance as an economic category and trace the stages of formation and formalization of this institution.

The study of the evolution and specifics of the economic and legal institution of insurance in a number of highly developed countries as a form of protection of economic and personal well-being made it possible to establish⁷⁴ that insurance is an institutional form of production relations and is a mechanism of subjective interaction in situations of economic damage generated by objective factors of the economic environment (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Evolution of the institution of insurance⁷⁵

As a result of the evolution of the institution of insurance, the following goals have been formed, which are reflected in the legislation on insurance:

- support of an economic entity by compensation for material damage provided for by the insurance contract, aimed at preserving production resources, i.e. respecting the interests of economic entities.

- monitoring the effective use of economic objects, designed to ensure the protection of the interests of all economic entities.

⁷⁴ Gubar O. V., Kukhmirov P. S. Impact of property transformation on the dynamics of insurance relations in Russia: Monograph. Rostov-on-Don: RSUE "RINH", 2000. p. 5-49 (- 167 p.),

⁷⁵ A number of scientific literatures have been compiled on the basis of synthesis, such as Gubar O. V. Impact of Property Transformation on the Dynamics of Insurance Relations in Russia: Monograph / O. V. Gubar, P. S. Kukhmirov. Rostov-on-Don: RSUE "RINH", 2000. p. 5-49 (- 167 p.); Natkhov T.V. Evolution of the Insurance Institute and Its Role in the System of Social Reproduction. Strakhovoe Delo, 31 (199) -2005, pp. 70-76; Frumina S. Compensatory Theories of Insurance: Evolution of Views. Bulletin of the Institute of Economics of the Russian Academy of Sciences. 2012. № 6. Pp. 134-142. etc.

In accordance with the objectives, insurance relations are intended to correct the situation of property or damage in such a way that, no matter what damage the objects of property of economic agents have suffered in advance, it has been fully or partially compensated in accordance with the insurance contract.

The economic category of insurance is characterized by the following features (Fig. 6):

- insurance relations have a probabilistic (risky) nature;
- insurance communities are formed from among insurers and insureds;

Fig.6. Insurance as an Economic Category: Nature and Features⁷⁶

- Funds of the insurance fund are formed at the expense of special premiums of the subjects, intended to compensate for pre-foreseeable damage;
- The funds of the insurance fund, unlike finance, can be presented in kind;
- the resources of the insurance fund can be redistributed only among a closed circle of persons;
- the material consequences of damage are redistributed among all payers of insurance premiums;
- insurance activities are self-sustaining;
- Life insurance combines risk and savings functions.

The risk function of insurance is considered by many researchers to be the main one, since the insurance risk (or probability of damage) "... is directly related to the main purpose of insurance to provide financial assistance to affected farms. It is within the framework of the risk function that the redistribution of the monetary form of value among insurance participants takes place in connection with the consequences of accidental insurance events."⁷⁷

The saving function of life insurance allows you to satisfy "... the need for insurance protection of the achieved family prosperity. This happens by organizing life insurance when accumulating under insurance contracts... stipulated insurance amounts".⁷⁸

Thus, acting in the form of money, fixing these relations by legal documents, insurance has features that connect it with the categories of "finance", "credit", and at the same time performs functions specifically characteristic only for it, and only its inherent role, which allows us to consider insurance as an independent economic category.

Today, insurance is not only a functional financial instrument, but also a stable economic and legal structure that adapts to the transformations of the market economy.

⁷⁶A number of scientific literatures are compiled on the basis of the synthesis, such as Odinokova T.D. Economic Essence of Insurance Taking into Account Evolutionary Theoretical Positions. Bulletin of the Academy of Knowledge No37 (2), 2020, pp. 463-470; Khudyakov A.I. Theory of Insurance. Moscow, Statut Publ., 2010. - 656 p.; Fogelson Y.B. Insurance Law: Theoretical Foundations and Practice of Application: Monograph. Moscow: Norma; INFRA-M, 2012. - 576 p. and others.

⁷⁷Reitman L.I. Strakhovoe delo [Insurance Business]. Moscow, ROST Publ., 2007. P. 17 (- 377 p.).

⁷⁸Romanova T.F. Insurance: Theory, Practice. Rostov-on-Don: RGEA, 1998. P. 15 (- 199 p.).

Conclusion.

In economic research, various points of view on insurance relations as a complex economic category are presented and a significant number of their definitions have been formulated. But despite this, even at present the question of the nature and boundaries of insurance relations belongs to the category of debatable. A set of theoretical, methodological and practical problems associated with the development of theoretical and empirical scientific knowledge on the problematic issue of insurance relations, the need for their regulation, including the development of proposals to increase the competitiveness of services in competition, determine the relevance of the study.

In scientific publications, despite the presence of practical examples, there is an insufficient theoretical understanding of the possibility of implementing insurance relations outside the traditionally formed and normatively fixed circle of their participants in the insurance market, there is no explanation of insurance relations outside the insurance market in the theory of insurance, and the possible impact of this phenomenon on the development of the insurance market as a whole is not analyzed.

Thus, insurance at the present stage of development is a system of economic relations, the main elements of which are the forms and methods of formation of trust funds and their use to compensate for damage occurring in case of unforeseen adverse phenomena (risks), or to assist citizens in the event of certain events in their lives.

As an element of the system of economic relations, insurance is closely related to business, which is characterized by a willingness to take risks, organizational and economic innovation and effective ways of using and preserving resources. The nature of business activity, as well as the vulnerability of the subject to external adverse influences, determine the emergence of certain insurance interests, which are fixed in the relevant insurance contracts.

The dynamics of insurance interests, in turn, determines the emergence of innovative forms of insurance and new types of insurance products.

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